

CHANGE IN FIBER LENGTH DURING THE STAGES OF THE SPINNING PROCESS

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Abstract. This article provides information on the change in fiber length along the transitions of the spinning process: length of the modal mass, length of the staple mass, average mass length, quadratic unevenness along the length.

Key words: fiber, cotton bale, spinning process, cotton yarn, staple mass length, quadratic unevenness.

Introduction. Geometric properties of cotton fiber include length and linear density. This is considered one of the most important indicators and one of the main properties of cotton spinning, which determines the quality of the yarns obtained from them. Because the longer the cotton fiber, the more thin, smooth and strong yarns are obtained from it. Thin and standard fibers are obtained from long fibers, and thick and poor-quality yarns with high unevenness are obtained from short and coarse fibers. It is known that the better the length, thinness, strength and other main properties of the fiber, the more mature and high-quality yarns are obtained from such fibers. It follows that thin yarns with normal strength can be obtained from long fibers. Less fiber is used for the production of thin yarns, resulting in higher economic efficiency of fiber use.

Methodology. It is known from the results of a number of scientific and research works that if the length of the cotton fibers is increased by 1 mm, the strength of the yarn will increase by 3-4%. This indicator is especially important for medium cotton fibers. Therefore, maintaining the natural length of cotton fibers during the production process is of great technological and economic importance. On the contrary, even if the length of cotton fibers is reduced by 1 g in cotton gins or yarn spinning plants, the spinning ability of the fiber decreases, as a result, the elongation at break of 1 km of the yarns obtained from it decreases.

If the length of cotton fiber is reduced even by a certain amount in spinning enterprises, it will have a negative effect on the quality of the yarns obtained from it. For example, in spinning enterprises, even if the fiber length is reduced by 0.5 mm, it will have a negative impact on the economic indicators of the enterprise.

In cotton ginning and spinning enterprises, the fiber is damaged by a number of technological processes, that is, it receives mechanical damage, which does not leave a negative impact on the quality of the fiber. Therefore, optimal options are selected for each technological process transition in cotton ginning and yarn spinning enterprises.

Results. Scientific and research work was carried out on the change of the length of the staple mass of the fiber during the spinning process. For this purpose, samples were taken from various mixtures in the process of yarn extraction at the spinning plant, the length of the staple mass was determined and compared to the initial sample (Table 1).

To the change of fiber length according to the transitions of the spinning process effect of mixture composition

Table 1

№	Products	Composition of the mixture, %					
		4-I-30%, 5-I-70%		4-II-60%, 5-I-40%		4-I-60%, 4-II-40%	
		Cotton bale	After cotton spinning	Cotton bale	After cotton spinning	Cotton bale	After cotton spinning
1.	Modal mass length, mm	29,0	28,1	30,6	29,9	29,2	28,8
2.	Staple mass length, mm	32,6	31,4	32,5	31,8	32,5	31,9
3.	Average mass length, mm	23,5	22,8	26,2	25,1	24,6	23,9
4.	quadratic unevenness in length, %	22,5	27,2	21,6	26,8	22,5	25,4

Based on the results of the research, in Figures 1 and 2, histograms of the influence of the different mixture composition on the length of the staple mass and square unevenness of the length of the fiber were constructed.

Composition of the mixture. **Figure 1.** The effect of the mixture composition on the change of the length of the staple mass of the fiber according to the transitions of the spinning process.

■ - Cotton bale;
 ■ - After cotton spinning.

Composition of the mixture. **Figure 2.** The influence of the composition of the mixture on the change of the quadratic unevenness of the length of the fiber during the transitions of the spinning process.

 - Cotton bale;
 - After cotton spinning.

Discussion. If we analyze the parameters of fiber length and quadratic unevenness during the spinning process transitions, 3.7% after the spinning process compared to the staple mass length of the cotton fiber in the 4-I-30%, 5-I-70% mixture decreased by 0.8 mm, the quadratic length unevenness increased by 17.3%, compared to the length of the staple mass of cotton fiber in the mixture 4-II-60%, 5-I-40% after spinning process 4, decreased by 2%, i.e. 1.1 mm, length quadratic unevenness increased by 19.4%, after spinning process of staple mass length of cotton fiber in 4-I-60%, 4-II-40% mixture. It decreased by 2.9%, that is, by 0.7 mm, the quadratic unevenness in length increased by 11.4%. As it can be seen from the results of the research, the length of the staple mass of cotton fiber decreased more in 4-II-60%, 5-I-40% mixture compared to other mixtures.

In order to obtain high-quality yarn at cotton spinning enterprises, first of all, it is necessary to correctly choose the type classification. In addition, the amount of defects and waste in the cotton fiber plays a big role. For example, the higher the amount of impurities in the fiber, the higher the quality of the yarn.

In spinning machines, the higher the number of interruptions during winding and forming, the higher the unevenness of the yarn. As a result of increased breakage of yarns, the employment of workers increases and the productivity of machines decreases.

Conclusion. The main reason for the decrease in the length of the staple mass of the fiber during the spinning process is the increase in the mechanical damage of the fiber, which affects not only the length of the fiber, but also the quality indicators of the yarns obtained from it. In conclusion, it was found that the length of the staple mass of the fiber in the composition of various mixtures decreased from 2.9% to 4.2% after the spinning process and the quadratic length unevenness increased from 11.4% to 19.4%.

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